

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' ECOLOGICAL CULTURE BY DIRECTING INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES USING STEAM TECHNOLOGY

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Abstract. *In this article, it is stated that STEAM educational technology is an educational technology that requires a thorough understanding of knowledge, practical experience and working on projects, and the ability to think independently and creatively. In order to ensure the continuity of training based on it, the ways of organizing training and directing students to ideas and innovations of an ecological nature in order to ensure the continuity of ongoing work are shown on the example of the "Ecological assistant" device.*

Keywords: *educational system, children's level of formation, STEAM educational technology, environmental protection, ecological education, Ecological auxiliary device, demonstration of abilities.*

Introduction. Major reforms are being implemented in new Uzbekistan in order to fundamentally change the education system, integrate it with international standards, train qualified personnel in line with the labor market demand, and bring up a new generation that will realize the idea of the Third Renaissance. The economic power of each country, the rise in the level of social and spiritual life is determined by the competitiveness of the educational system and the development of science. The orientation of the economy of the countries to the development of the creative industry requires the importance of using educational technologies that develop the qualities that are important and necessary for the majority of future professions. As President Sh. Mirziyoyev noted, We should interest our children in professions, art and culture. It is necessary to form students' free and creative thinking, teamwork and communication skills [1].

Of course, the level of formation of children depends on the knowledge, skills and qualifications they have acquired in the family and in educational institutions. That is why it is very important to give students the knowledge based on the above requirements. That is, the educational process should be organized in such a way that the given educational and upbringing processes are consistent and integrated. The educational technology used in such a process should be a guarantee of achieving the goal. One of such educational technologies is STEAM educational technology.

STEAM educational technology aims to create interconnected and integrated curricula designed to support innovation in lifelong learning. STEAM Technology stands for "Science and Technology Interpreted Through Engineering and the Arts Based on Mathematical Elements", and each subject is designed to combine theoretical and practical skills based on the integration of these five disciplines. The child covers several fields of knowledge at the same time, gets the opportunity to use the given information, check the facts in his own experience.

Methods. Georgette described it as "STEAM - an educational technology based on elements of science and technology, engineering and mathematics, combined with fun through the arts."

Modern children live in the era of information and computerization. In a rapidly changing life, a person is required not only to acquire knowledge, but also, first of all, to thoroughly understand this knowledge, to work on practical experience and projects, and to have the ability to think independently and creatively. Not only adults, but also preschool children are actively using any technological innovations. Every child is a potential inventor. From a young age, children are interested in motorized and moving toys, robotics, working with construction materials, experiments with living and inanimate nature, trying to understand how they are made and work by breaking their toys, that is; they try to find answers to such questions as why the wheels turn, the lights turn on, and the sound is made. Properly organized technical creativity of children allows to satisfy interest and attract the younger generation to useful practical activities.

Through STEAM - educational technology, a child develops creativity, diligence, curiosity and the most important feature - problem-solving skills. "STEAM thinking" starts from childhood. From the time when the child does not know how to walk, he begins to understand the connection, sequence and probability of processes. These characteristics require comprehensive encouragement by adults, timely imparting of necessary knowledge, skills, competences and values. Modules of STEAM technology, Digital technologies - give them another opportunity to show their creativity and learning ability.

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STEAM is an integrated interdisciplinary approach that explores STEM subjects through inquiry, creative thinking, and liberal arts problem solving. So while STEAM projects are science-based, they leave room for curiosity, imagination, and artistic expression. As an approach, STEAM education aims to encourage a child's creativity and self-expression, as well as develop their statistical and numerical abilities, as well as problem-solving and critical thinking skills [3].

Results. 2In 2019, Uzbekistan adopted the concepts of environmental protection and development of ecological education until 2030.

Also, in the same year, the implementation of work related to solid household waste in the period of 2019-2028 and the strategies of the transition to the "green" economy of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the period of 2019-2030 were also approved. In addition, problems related to soil pollution with various industrial and household wastes, atmospheric air pollution, and the negative impact of the activities of industrial enterprises on the environment are still relevant in the field of environmental safety. Also, the issue related to the rational use of water resources in the agricultural sector, industry and communal economy remains one of the sore points.

It is necessary to develop programs in the field of environmental protection and waste management in every region and enterprise and ensure their unconditional implementation [4]. Everyone should have their place in this. In particular, the activities carried out in the field of education are of great importance in this regard, and teaching students to protect the environment

from a young age is one of the most urgent issues. Improving the effectiveness of the educational work is the cooperation of parents, especially the instructions and explanations of educators and science teachers on maintaining environmental stability, directing them to free creative work, and organizing their free time effectively is important.

Therefore, in order to develop the above abilities of students from a young age, it is possible to direct students to various ideas and innovations aimed at the implementation of the above goals, providing continuity of activities based on STEAM technology in extracurricular activities and clubs. We recommend the following in order to support the development of innovative ideas [5-10] and the creation of devices that will in some sense "help" in the protection of the environment and the timely collection of waste in the regions.

Discussions. One such device is the "Ecological Assistant" device [11] and its preparation.

Preparation of an ecological auxiliary device. Required equipment and tools: ESP 32 (Wf variant), Voltage reduction module LM2596, Ultrasonic HYSRF05, GPS NEO-7M module, 18650 battery slot in 2 variants, 18650 Li-ion batteries 2 pcs, Solar panel 9V/2W, Li-ion batteries u-n charge (capacity) indicator 2S, charging module for Li-ion batteries 2S option, switch-connectors. Soldering device, connector wires.

How to assemble the device:

Let's start by assembling the scheme of the device shown in Figure 1.

1. *The Trig* pin of the Ultrasonic HYSRF05 is connected to pin 12 of the ESP 32, and the Echo pin is connected to pin 14.

2. The RXD and TXD terminals of the GPS NEO-7M module are connected to the RX0 and TX0 terminals of the ESP 32, respectively.

3. Before 18650 Li-ion batteries are inserted into the battery slot, the negative part is connected to the IN - part of the step-down module LM2596. And the positive part is connected to the IN+ end after connecting to the input and output parts of the switch-connector.

4. The positive (+) and negative (-) ends of the solar panel are connected to the positive (+) and - ends of the charging module for 18650 batteries respectively.

5. The + and negative (-) ends of the charge indicator and the B+ and B- ends of the charging module for 18650 batteries are connected to the + and - ends of the 18650 Li-ion batteries respectively.

6. By connecting a voltmeter to the OUT + and OUT - terminals of the step-down module LM2596, the voltage is adjusted to 5V by screwing the connector clip of the step-down module with a screwdriver.

7. The OUT + end of the voltage-reducing module LM2596 is connected to VIN of ESP 32, the OUT - end is connected to GNG of ESP 32. VCC terminals of Ultrasonic HYSRF05 and GPS NEO-7M module are connected to VIN terminal of ESP 32 and GNG terminals are connected to GNG terminals.

After the general scheme of the device is prepared, a specially prepared program is loaded into the ESP 32 using the Arduino IDE 2.3.2 computer program.

Before loading the program, it is necessary to select the ESP32-WROOM-DA Module panel from the COM section to which the ESP 32 is connected. After writing the program, the device is tested in test mode. As you can see, the device is ready for operation.

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